

Intricacies Involved With Detoxification Of Drinking Water

- **Hari Krishna Garg**
Dept. of Zoology, Sarojini Naidu Govt. Girls Post Graduate
(Autonomous) College, Bhopal
- **Jaya Garg**
Oriental Institute of Science & Technology, Bhopal

Blue-green algae comprise an old subdivision of microscopic organisms, settled in a large variety of environments such as freshwaters, sea, oceans, rocks, soil and hot springs. In freshwaters, some are benthic, but many are found on the surface, floating at the mercy of winds and water currents. Under enriched conditions, these unicellular microscopic entities multiply profusely, aggregate together and form scums. On lysis, they produce toxins that are not easily inactivated by laboratory equivalents of water purification process viz. flocculation-filtration-chlorination treatment. Even activated carbon, in low doses, falls short to yield desirable results. However, colossal amount of charcoal can do so. Furthermore, activated carbon filtration, in combination with ionization, has been found effective in deactivating toxins.

Though toxic degradations have been likely, yet the present state of techniques seem inadequate to exterminate cent-per-cent algae from raw water entering the supply system. Normally, slow sand-filters are considered to be more dependable than fast filters in doing away with phytoplankton. *Albeit*, the slow filters do not remove color from water as some cyanophytes succeed in penetrating the filtration bed. Moreover, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, at the closing stages of bloom formation secretes substantial amount of organic compounds with polysaccharide base. This dross is seldom removed by traditional treatments like sand-filtration, $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ coagulation, $FeCl_3$ flocculation, sedimentation, etc. and much of it goes into the water supply, making the water distasteful to users.

While there is no way to deal with these nuisance microphytes, use of blue stone $CuSO_4$ in block or granular form can be recommended as an algicide. However, the same cannot be used beyond a certain limit and that too in a large basin. Of course, ionization at the end of filtration may be a good permutation to get rid of plant organisms with their associated organoleptic properties.

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